

Tracing the Journey from Intention to Behavior in Green Purchases: A Bibliometric Analysis

Shivika Kaushik¹ and Sanjeev Kumar Sharma²

¹Research Scholar, Corresponding Author; University Institute of Applied Management Sciences (UIAMS) Panjab University, Chandigarh, India.

Email:ID: Shivikachd@gmail.com

ORCID ID: 0009-0002-9602-8560.

²Professor, University Institute of Applied Management Sciences (UIAMS) Panjab University, Chandigarh, India

ABSTRACT

Green purchase intention is the desire of a consumer to purchase environmentally friendly products in comparison with the traditional ones. Attitude, intention to purchase is also discontinuous to actual purchasing behavior and therefore it is essential to reduce attitude behavior gap to achieve the consumer perception towards green products. Green purchase behavior involves the purchasing and consumption of the products and services that have least environmental impact. Fast moving consumer goods refer to the commodities which can be sold in single instance at low prices due to the high turnover and demand. Principal business divisions of united Fast-Moving consumer goods include food and drink, health care, home and personal services. One of the psychological models is theory of planned behavior that has gained popularity in the marketing field in an attempt to bridge attitude and behavior by the use of intention. The central subject of the paper is to synthesize the information on the green purchase behavior based on the bibliometric review of 646 papers published between 2000 and 12 November 2025 and to display the findings in a concise way. This paper relied on Scopus database to map the key recent trends in green purchase behavior. It was also noted that the keywords such as the green purchase behavior, the green purchase intention, the theory of planned behavior, the fast-moving consumer goods and customer satisfaction has had an impressive coverage to the green marketing over the past ten years

Keywords: Green purchase behavior, theory of planned behavior (TPB), fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) green purchase intention, and customer satisfaction..

INTRODUCTION:

Environmental issues including overpopulation, deforestation, increase in carbon dioxide, greenhouse gases, damages to wildlife, environmental degradation, and global warming are well known. Increase in production processes and manufacturing activities are polluting the worldwide environment. These environmental problems have created a requirement to practice business in a sustainable manner. Greater attention to environmental issues serves as evidence that environmental concern is a major emerging concern for strategy makers and businesses (Kilbourne & Polonsky,2005). The term "sustainable development" came in order to protect stakeholders and the environment. Sustainable development is linked with business activities and practices that help to attain sustainability in the environment. Businesses are becoming more aware about practices, actions and their effects and are investing more towards environmental protection issues (United Nations,2012). The demand for green products and consumer concern for environment gave rise to the evolution of novel marketing term known as 'Green Marketing' (Peattie & Charter, 1997).

According to the (Crisil Ratings report 2025), revenue growth in the fast-moving consumer goods sector in India

is expected to increase to 6-8% in FY26 from an extremely low 5-6% in FY25. Green Marketing means when an organization attempts to manufacture, market, price and distribute goods in a manner which does not degrade the environment (Pride & Ferrell, 1993). Due to environmental revolution, there is a massive shift in environmental consciousness and consumer behavior which has led to increased demand for green FMCG products. Organizations can choose between green FMCG products range, mix of environmentally friendly products and traditional product offering. (Ohtomo & Hirose,2007) recommended that in case consumers are not aware of green FMCG products, there is an attitude- behavior gap. (Ajzen & manstead,2007) observed that tpb is widely used to find out reasons behind people's actions and intentions. "According to theory of planned behavior, behavior has a direct influence on behavior intention. The theory of planned behavior has established three antecedents of behavioral intention which are subjective norms attitude and perceived behavioral control."

"Attitude has been the main element affecting willingness to purchase in the context of a green product". "Earlier studies have employed the TPB" "framework to bridge gap between attitude and behavior (Piligrimiene et al., 2020)." Green purchase behavior pertains to buying sustainable products and neglecting those that are detrimental to the environment. (Chan,2001)""." In the

present era, customers pay more for eco-friendly products than for traditional products."While going for shopping consumers verifying whether the product is made out of recyclable materials and then they purchase products that are environmentally friendly (Pagliacci et al., 2019)". "Some researchers have conducted studies to gain insight into pro-environmental behavior (Kim et al., 2013; Han et al., 2010)". "Future research on green purchase behavior is necessary in context of emerging markets as purchase behavior changes from time to time." Young consumers are changing their consumption patterns due to increased awareness towards environmental concerns (Adnan et al., 2017; Kautish and Sharma, 2019a). Developing economies are an emerging market for environmentally friendly products, but developed economies are still in their infancy (Khare, 2015).

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Green purchasing behavior implies purchasing and consuming products that are useful for the environment. (Mostafa,2007). (Kumar,2016) divided previous review of literature into thematic areas such as co-orientation, green marketing strategy and green marketing functions. "(Saleem et al.,2021) conducted a bibliometric analysis of articles regarding green marketing published between 1977 and 2020 in order to capture the current state of the literature in green marketing". A literature review of the published articles between 1990 and 2021 was conducted by (Kar & Harichandan, 2022) in Scopus and Web of sciences databases. The findings suggested that eco-tourism, green marketing techniques and sustainable marketing are becoming significant. (Geels et al.,2015) employed bibliographical coupling to classify authors, documents and journals. The methodology used in this research has been used in previous bibliometric papers (Bhardwaj et al.,2023; Saleem et al.,2021; Donthu et al.,2021; Wang et al.,2022; Kar & Harichandan.,2022). (Sharma.,2021) developed a green purchase decision making model and gave an overview of green marketing. This study will provide an in-depth overview and diverse perspectives on green purchase behavior. There are various methods to assess and evaluate the quality and quantity in any research-based field. Bibliometric analysis was selected for this paper as it depicts the publishing trends and emerging patterns in a particular field (Durisin et al.,2010). Major benefit of conducting a bibliometric analysis is that it can assess the published study directly without reaching out to the authors. (Garfield.,1979). Previous bibliometric analysis was conducted on keywords like "Green marketing", "Green Consumer behavior" "Green marketing in marketing and related fields" but no study was conducted on "Green purchase behavior", thus this research tries to fill this research gap in area of marketing research. Since there exist gap between attitude, intention and actual purchasing behavior so, we need to find and keep track of the most recent progress in this area. It can be achieved by utilizing the biggest indexing and abstracting database, Scopus, to find relevant keywords and look for areas that are left unexplored in previous bibliometric studies.

"Thus, it may be utilized to gather significant findings on green purchase behavior". "There is a lack of research on

bibliometric analysis in green purchase behavior since most of the studies in this area focused on systematic literature review"." (Lestari et al.,2023; Sharma et al.,2022; Mahalingam et al.,2024; Yusoff et al.,2024; Wijekoon & Sabri.,2021).

A comprehensive study is needed in green purchasing behavior to fill the attitude-behavior gap. Thus, we have utilized a lot of different keywords that are discussed in methodology section. As compared to traditional literature review, bibliometric analyses provide three major advantages. First, the bibliometric analysis offers a general understanding of a particular research area such as the most prolific author, most cited article as well as different themes of research. Second, such studies may develop a strong research pillar to develop a research field in unique directions i.e. by offering theoretical background and the primary research directions of a research field. Third, such analyses enable researchers to examine emerging areas, identify gaps in different articles and research constituents like carrying out research within the clusters that has not yet been explored. Bibliometric analysis is one of the most common methods of determining and analyzing a vast amount of scientific information, through this approach, scholars can determine the evolutionary peculiarities of a certain field and concentrate on the future directions within the same field (Donthu et al., 2021). In short, it helps in creating meaning to massive unstructured data. (Donthu et al., 2021). The present bibliometric review of 646 articles released in the last twenty-five years (2000- 2025) will present statistical and factual information on the current research trends on the topic of the green purchase behavior by investigating the most active countries, authors and organizations.

Following research objectives have been developed which are as follow:

- To explore the publishing patterns in green purchase behavior in last twenty-five years.
- To determine the top journals in green purchase behavior.
- To assess the most productive countries, organizations and authors in green purchase behavior.
- To examine the frequently used keywords and key trends in green purchase behavior.
- To provide the implications for marketers, service providers and policy makers in order to get better insights into green purchase behavior.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Methods

This paper employed bibliographic analysis method to identify, comprehend and evaluate the publishing patterns in green purchase behavior. Bibliometrics is an analytical technique that offers an in-depth and transparent

understanding of publication patterns and intellectual developments across research papers, articles, and scholarly documents. (Rashmi and Kataria, 2021).

3.2 Database Selection

"Several types of databases are available for indexing and abstraction". Two major types of databases exist multidisciplinary databases such as Scopus and Web of Science and subject-specific databases such as Medline PubMed, Agricola, and Eric (Thomas, 2021)" Scopus was also chosen among the listed databases since it is the largest database in the world. In our study, we used Scopus, which is a summarization of scientific data, provides reliable indexing, and presents quality articles (Pranckuté, 2021). The number of citations on goggle scholar may be different. It contains theses, conference papers, reviews, books and book chapters as well as items which are yet to be published. Such content is not indexed by Scopus; therefore, it does not add to the number of citations. This implies that articles that are indexed in

Scopus would always be having less citations compared to the ones that are indexed in Google Scholar. This does not influence the credibility of the findings. This research covered qualitative and quantitative dimensions (Ryser, 2021). Some publications were also not found in other subject-specific databases during the data retrieval procedure because the Scopus database might have used similar words and provided the same information

3.3 "Search Query"

In this study, "Scopus database" was used to conduct research.

The following keyword search was run in the Scopus core collection's topic field (TS):- ("Green" AND "Purchase behavior") OR ("TPB" OR "FMCG") AND ("Purchase intention" OR "Customer satisfaction")

The query was run on 12 November 2025, at Panjab University Chandigarh.

Figure 1: Formulation of Core Terms and Concepts

3.4 Criteria for Inclusion and Exclusion

A thorough evaluation needs to follow and comply with standard requirements given in PRISMA (Page et al.,2021). The PRISMA standards states that the articles should be examined sequentially and are handled in an identical way after the initial verification process. We examined 646 research papers from the Scopus database that were published between 2000 to 12 November 2025 against the mentioned keywords.

Identified papers were examined using the mentioned three step process which is as follow:

1. Identifying, correcting and eliminating duplicate articles (Chistov et al.,2021)

2. Checking and reading the articles based on title, keyword criteria and abstract.
3. Analyzing the research articles as per exclusion and inclusion criteria.

We excluded thesis and dissertation, subject area not relevant to the domain, conference paper, book chapter, review and conference review, languages other than English, articles in press and conference proceedings, book, book series and journal.

3.5 “Bibliometric Analysis”

This last section depicts the results of a bibliographic analysis of green purchasing behavior that was published from 2000 to November 12, 2025. Several software programs are used for bibliometric analysis, such as Cite Space, RStudio (Bibliometrics package), Bib Excel, Vos viewer, Gephi, and HistCite (Ampah et al., 2021). This study employed Vos viewer and Biblioshiny for data

analysis. Vos viewer was specifically utilized to classify the groups and map the domain across disciplines so that people from different backgrounds may readily comprehend what was found. (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010). Additionally, cluster analysis was utilized to categorize and divide the bibliometric data into smaller, homogeneous groupings to enhance interpretation and comparison (Caruso et al., 2021) We used a number of tools and software’s to analyze the data, such as Microsoft Excel, R studio, Biblioshiny and VOS Viewer.

4 Results: “Systematic Analysis of Green purchase behavior”

4.1 Annual scientific production

"Figure 3: Annual scientific production in green purchase behavior"

Figure 3 shows the publication trends in green purchase behavior over the last twenty-five years. The data revealed that the number of publications remained negligible during the early period (2000–2014), with fewer than five articles per year, indicating that the green purchase behavior had not yet gained significant academic attention. A gradual increase can be seen after 2014, with a steady rise in publications which reached about 10 articles by 2017 and about 15 by 2019. The number of

publications was increased after 2020 from around 18 in 2020 to about 90 in 2023. The research articles peaked in 2024 with more than 100 publications, indicating a significant increase in scholarly interest in green purchase behavior.

4.2 Average Citations per year in green purchase behavior

Figure 4: Average citations per year in green purchase behavior

Table no 1: Top 10 most cited documents in green purchase behavior

<i>S No.</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Journal</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Total Citations</i>
1	"Predicting green product consumption using theory of planned behavior and reasoned action"	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	Paul, Justin; Modi, Ashwin G Patel, Jayesh D.	2016	1636
2	"Factors influencing the adoption of internet banking: An integration of TAM and TPB with perceived risk and perceived benefit"	Electronic Commerce Research and Applications	Lee, Mingchi	2009	1471
3	"Determinants of Consumers' Green Purchase Behavior in a Developing Nation: Applying and Extending the Theory of Planned Behavior"	Ecological Economics	Yadav, Rambalak; Pathak, Govind Swaroop.	2017	967
4	"Determinants of Chinese consumers' green purchase behavior"	Psychology and Marketing	Chan, Ricky Y.K.	2001	904
5	"An investigation of green hotel customers' decision formation: Developing an extended model of the theory of planned behavior"	International Journal of Hospitality Management	Han, Heesup; Kim, Yunhi	2010	766
6	"Green purchasing behavior: A conceptual framework and empirical investigation of Indian consumers"	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	Jaiswal, Deepak; Kant, Rishi.	2018	598

7	Impact of culture, behavior and gender on green purchase intention"	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	Sreen, Naman; Purbey, Shankar; Sadarangani, Pradip H.	2018	559
8	"Consumer purchase intention for organic personal care products"	Journal of Consumer Marketing	Kim, Hee-yeon; Chung, Jaecun	2011	552
9	"Application of the extended theory of planned behavior model to investigate purchase intention of green products among Thai consumers".	Sustainability (Switzerland)	Maichum, Kamonthip; Parichatnon, Surakiat; Peng, Kechung.	2016	535
10	"Theory of planning behavior (TPB) and customer satisfaction in the continued use of e- service: An integrated model"	Computers in Human Behavior	Liao, Chechen; Chen, Jianliang; Yen, David C.	2007	525

"Table 1 highlights the top 10 most cited documents in green purchase behavior". "This table shows that the total number of citations is rising up". "According to table 1, articles except for (Lee.,2009), (Liao et al.,2006) all research work deals with green purchase behavior and green purchase intention". "Theory of planned behavior is major framework used in explaining the relationship between intention and behavior". "Major countries contributing in these top 10 articles are India, China and Thailand". "This indicates the growing global interest in green consumption". "The major contributing journals are

journal of retailing and consumer services, electronic commerce research and applications, ecological economics, psychology and marketing, international journal of hospitality management, journal of consumer marketing, sustainability (Switzerland) and computers in human behavior".

4.4 Top 15 countries in green purchase behavior (2000-2025)

Figure 6: Top 15 countries in green purchase behavior (2000-2025)

Figure 6 shows influential countries in terms of articles published between 2000 to 2025. We considered the research work of top 15 countries related to green purchase behavior. India, China and Malaysia are the top 3 countries in green purchase behavior and they have

published (312 articles). One of the important findings is that there is high growth in developing countries like India (134 publications) and low productivity in countries such as Bangladesh and South Africa (only 15 publications)

4.5 Top 15 Research-Producing Institutions in green purchase behavior

Figure 7: Top 15 Research-Producing Institutions in green purchase behavior

Figure 7 shows major research institutes in green purchase behavior. Out of the 646 articles included in the study, these 15 institutions produced 123 only (19%). The top research institute in green purchase behavior is Universiti Sains Malaysia producing a total number of 13 documents followed by National Economics university Hanoi with 12 documents and The Hong Kong polytechnical university by 11 documents. Next 3 universities that is Taylor's university Malaysia, OP Jindal global university and graduate school of business produced a consistent of 10 documents. INTI international university published only

8 documents. University Utara Malaysia, Vietnam National University Hanoi and University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City produced 7 documents. Next 3 Universities produced a constant number of 6 documents. However, 5 documents were produced by Universiti Teknologi MARA and King Abdulaziz university. One of the important findings from this graph suggests that green purchase behavior is mainly studied in Asian countries due to rapid economic growth, increased emphasis on environmental concerns, green products and sustainability as a development priority.

4.6 Prominent Authors

Figure no 8: Most Prominent authors in green purchase behavior

As is evident in Figure 8, the most prominent author in green purchase behavior is Bhutto my from North American University and Liu Y from Michigan State university with 6 documents each. Duong cd from national economics university Vietnam and Khan A from

Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi both contributed 5 documents each. There are several authors such as Kumar a, Soomro ya, Sreen n, Wang J, Wang L and Wang S with 4 documents each

4.7 Prominent Journals

S.NO	Sources	Articles
1	Sustainability (Switzerland)	68
2	Journal of retailing and consumer services	17
3	Journal of cleaner production	15
4	Journal of Islamic marketing	14
5	Foods	11
6	Cogent business and management	10
7	Business strategy and the environment	9
8	International journal of environmental research and public health	9
9	Cleaner and responsible consumption	8
10	Management of environmental quality	8

Table no 2- Most prominent journals in green purchase behavior

"Table 2 shows the top 10 prominent journals in green purchase behavior. Sustainability (Switzerland) is the top journal with (68 articles), followed by Journal of retailing and consumer services (17 articles), Journal of cleaner production (15 articles), Journal of Islamic marketing (14 articles), Foods (11 articles) and Cogent business and

management (10 articles)". "Other prominent journals are Business strategy and the environment (9 articles), international journal of environmental research and public health (9 articles), Cleaner and responsible consumption (8 articles) and Management of environmental quality (8 articles).

4.8 Co-Authorship

Figure no- 9 shows the co-authorship network as visualized by Vos viewer. In this visualization nodes represent authors and linkages shows the collaborative publications among the authors. The red clusters include the authors such as Das, Manish; Strong, Carolyn A.; Sivapalan, Achchuthan; Jebarajakirthy, Charles; Maseeh, Haroon Iqbal; and Ashaduzzaman, Md shows strong collaborative relation among the authors. The green cluster on right comprises Sreen, Naman; Sadarangani, Pradip H.; Chatterjee, Swetapurna; and Purbey, Shankar. The authors in this cluster have active collaboration with other authors. The blue cluster represents the authors like Kumar, Sushant; Bhardwaj, Seema; and Chitnis, Asmita. This cluster connects the red cluster with green cluster and bridges the gap between the other clusters. The yellow

Figure no 9: Co- Authorship

cluster indicates limited collaboration by authors in green purchase behavior due to limited focus on sustainability

4.9 Co- Citation between Cited Sources

Figure no 10- Co- Citation between Cited Sources

Figure no-10 displays the journal co-citation network as seen in Vos-viewer. The nodes depict the journals and linkages shows co-citation relationships between them. The red cluster mostly include Journals related to marketing and consumer research including the Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science, Psychology & Marketing, and the Journal of International Consumer Marketing. This indicates stronger emphasis on consumer behavior. The green cluster on the top covers leading marketing and business journals, such as Journal of Business Research and the European Journal of Marketing. The blue cluster includes journals related to psychology such as the British Journal of Social Psychology, the Journal of Applied Social Psychology, and the Journal of Consumer Psychology. This shows that green purchase behavior is related to psychological aspects. The area is multidisciplinary because there are strong linkages across clusters that bring together ideas from marketing, business, and psychology.

5 DISCUSSION

Over the past few decades' governments, companies and public are becoming increasingly aware about the environmental issues which has led to increase in green marketing or sustainable marketing (Williams,2022). Green purchase behavior and green purchase intention are crucial prerequisites for green marketing. Government tries to minimize the environmental damage caused by industrial practices through implementing favorable taxes and rules. From the study's findings, it can be understood that people started buying more green products after 2015. The major prominent journals in green purchase behavior are Sustainability (Switzerland), journal of retailing and consumer services, journal of cleaner production, journal of Islamic marketing, foods and cogent business and management. It is important to encourage sustainable and ethical consumption in order to reduce the adverse environmental consequences and market green products (M. Han & Xu,2021). This study tries to assess the existing research by sequentially identifying,

consolidating and analyzing the green purchase behavior. Thus, it acts as a benchmark for guiding future research to gain practical and theoretical advances in green purchase behavior.

6 IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

"This study has advanced the domain of green purchase behavior by examining 646 published articles in peer-reviewed journals from Scopus to identify the most influential keywords top journals and publishing trends". From the findings it is clear that there is a gradual progress in green purchase behavior from 2000 to 2025 due to rising environmental awareness. This implies that marketers must integrate sustainability into their marketing strategies in order to remain competitive in marketplace. Service Providers can leverage green purchase behavior by offering eco-friendly services, distinct green labels, and incentives that enhances customer engagement and builds their trust. Policymakers can foster green purchase behavior by offering incentives, favorable laws, awareness campaigns and educating consumers regarding the environmental values. This study's data visualizations indicate that green marketing researchers may engage and influence the design strategies on recent themes developed in green purchase behavior (Gustavo et al., 2021). Thus, based on present study's findings we would like to recommend some future prospects in green purchase behavior. Further studies can focus on unexplored areas like cross cultural differences in green purchase behavior, digital green marketing strategies, and role of emerging technologies in promoting sustainability. This study relied solely on "Scopus database" which may limit the overall coverage of green purchase behavior, as the affiliated university provided the access only to this database. Future studies may enhance the findings by incorporating different databases like "web of science" or a blend of "Scopus and web of science", thereby reducing the potential database bias. Further studies may include qualitative aspects and mixed-methods to supplement quantitative techniques highlighted in this bibliometric analysis. "The bibliometric analysis shows that most studies are cross-sectional. Future research should use longitudinal study to track changes in consumer behavior over time."

CONCLUSION

"This study analyzed the existing literature published on green purchase behavior". "Both developed and developing nations must focus on green marketing research in order to foster sustainable consumption (Hosta & Zabkar, 2020)". "No bibliometric study was conducted from 2000 to 2025 for "Scopus" database using the keywords mentioned in methodology section that describes and summarize the advancement in green purchase behavior". "This study also identified the top authors, published articles, and top journals in green purchase behavior". Based on the findings of the study, we can recommend some top journals for future research in green purchase behavior such as Sustainability (Switzerland), journal of retailing and consumer services, journal of cleaner production, journal of Islamic marketing, foods and cogent business and management. "These are potential avenues for academic research in

green purchase behavior and related fields". "This study analyzed 646 published papers in peer reviewed journals from "Scopus database" in order to explore new insights into green purchase behavior and contributing to the body of knowledge".

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

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